

ACTION OF *p*-TOLUENE-SULPHONYL CHLORIDE ON POLYNITRO-OXY-DIPHENYLS

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The action of *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride on 3 : 5-dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl and 3 : 5 : 4'-trinitro-4-oxydiphenyl has been examined.

In each case a chloro compound has been obtained in the presence of diethylaniline as the condensing reagent. 3 : 5-Dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl forms also a *p*-toluene-sulphonate in the presence of sodium carbonate as the condensing reagent.

The action of various amines and amino compounds on these chloro compounds has also been studied.

It is well known that *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride reacts with nitrophenols in two ways (Ullman and Nadai, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1870, 3932; Ullman and Bruick, 1909, 42, 3939; Ullman and Sane, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 37; Sane and Joshi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2481; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 299; Sane, Chakravarty and Pramanick, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 55; Sane and Joshi, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 59; 1933, 10, 459; Joshi, *ibid.*, 1933, 10, 313). Mononitrophenols yield *p*-toluene-sulphonic esters in the presence of sodium carbonate or diethylaniline as the condensing reagent. Polynitrophenols, specially containing nitro groups in the 2:4 or 2:6 position to OH, also yield such esters in the presence of sodium carbonate as the condensing reagent, but are converted mainly into polynitro-chlorobenzenes, the OH group being replaced by Cl, in the presence of diethylaniline as the condensing reagent.

The chloro compounds as well as the toluene-sulphonyl esters, obtained from these polynitrophenols, are extremely reactive (Sane and Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 59; 1933, 10, 459). When treated with various amines and amino compounds like aniline, toluidines, pyridine, piperidine, aminophenols, dimethylamine, anisidines, etc., in alcoholic, benzene or toluene solution, they form condensation products.

In the present paper, the above reaction has been extended to 3 : 5-dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl and 3 : 5 : 4'-trinitro-4-oxydiphenyl. In the presence of diethylaniline as the condensing reagent, each of these nitrophenols forms a polynitro-chloro compound. 3 : 5-Dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl yields a *p*-toluene-sulphonyl ester in the presence of sodium carbonate as the condensing reagent.

The chloro compounds, so obtained, are found to be extremely reactive. They have been treated with various amines and the compounds formed isolated and characterised.

EXPERIMENTAL

3 : 5-Dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl was obtained by the nitration 4-oxydiphenyl in acetic acid solution with nitric acid (*d* 1.2) according to the method of Garcia Banns (*Chem. Abs.*, 1923, 770), m.p. 154°.

3 : 5-Dinitrodiphenyl-4-*p*-toluene sulphonate.—3 : 5-Dinitrodiphenyl (2.6 g.) and *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride (2 g.) were suspended in about 25 c.c. of hot water in a flask and then solid sodium carbonate was added to it in small quantities. Addition of sodium carbonate each time produced an orange colouration, which disappeared on heating. When the further addition of sodium carbonate did not produce any colouration, the reaction is

complete. The solution was then cooled, and the reaction product formed was filtered and washed with water. It was then recrystallised twice from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 158°, yield 3.4 g. (Found: N, 6.3; S, 7.4. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ require N, 6.7; S, 7.7 per cent).

3 : 5-Dinitro-4-chlorodiphenyl.—3 : 5-Dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl (2.6 g.), *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride (2 g.) and diethylaniline (10 c.c.) were heated together in a flask for 4 hours. The mixture was then cooled and the chloro compound isolated in the usual way. Colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 111°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 10.3. $C_{11}H_9O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 10.1 per cent).

3 : 5 : 4'-Trinitro-4-oxydiphenyl was obtained by the further nitration of 3 : 5-dinitro-4-oxydiphenyl in acetic acid solution, with excess of concentrated nitric acid (*d* 1.4) and warming, the solution was then cooled and diluted with water. The solid which separated out was filtered, dried and then recrystallised from toluene, m.p. 205° (Garcia Banus, *loc. cit.*).

In Table I the various compounds obtained from the two chloro compounds are described.

TABLE I

Reactants.	Formulas of compounds formed.	M.p.	Colour.	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Calc.
(i) With 3 : 5-dinitro-4-chlorodiphenyl					
Aniline	X.NH.C ₆ H ₅	165°	Deep scarlet	12.9	12.60
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	X.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃	179	Deep orange	12.3	12.03
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	X.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃	146	Yellowish orange	12.2	12.03
Dimethylamine	X.N(CH ₃) ₂	94	Orange yellow	14.7	14.60
Piperidine	X.N.C ₅ H ₁₀	124	Yellow	12.2	12.70
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	X.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	188	Red	11.1	11.50
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	X.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .OH	170	Brown	11.4	11.90
Ammonia	X.NH ₃	232	Turmeric yellow	16.4	16.30
(ii) With 3 : 5 : 4'-trinitro-4-chlorodiphenyl					
Aniline	Y.NH.C ₆ H ₅	199°	Orange yellow	14.2	14.70
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Y.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃	169	Orange	13.7	14.10
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	Y.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃	198	Brick red	13.7	14.10
Dimethylamine	Y.N(CH ₃) ₂	159	Yellow	17.4	16.90
Piperidine	Y.N.C ₅ H ₁₀	199	Lemon yellow	14.7	15.00
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	Y.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	212	Red	14.7	14.10
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	Y.NH.C ₆ H ₄ .OH	208	Red orange	13.6	13.20
Ammonia	Y.NH ₃	280	Yellow	18.3	18.40

3 : 5 : 4'-Trinitro-4-chlorodiphenyl.—3 : 5 : 4'-Trinitro-4-oxydiphenyl (3 g.), *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride (2 g.) and diethylaniline (20 c.c.) were heated together in a flask on the

water-bath for 4 hours. The mixture was then cooled, acidified with hydrochloric acid, washed with dilute sodium carbonate and then with water. The chloro compound was then isolated in the usual way and recrystallised twice from acetic acid, m.p. 171°. (Found: N, 12.8. $C_{12}H_8O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 13.0 per cent).

Reactivity of the Chloro Compounds.—The calculated quantities of the chloro compound and the amine (slight excess) were dissolved separately in alcohol, benzol or toluol and then mixed and refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solvent was then distilled off, the excess of amine removed by the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solid which separated out was washed thoroughly with boiling water and then recrystallised from a suitable solvent (alcohol, benzol or glacial acetic acid).

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